

The Mediating Effect of Organizational Efficacy on The Relationship Between Ethical Climate and Team Member Effectiveness: Law Enforcement Agency in Context

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Abstract:- The main thrust of the study was to find out the significance of the mediation of organizational efficacy on the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers. The researcher utilized the quantitative, non-experimental design using correlational technique. The respondents were the 367 police non-commissioned officers of Davao City Police Office through stratified random sampling. Adapted questionnaires were administered through online and data were retrieved via Google forms. To analyze the data and answer the study objectives statistical tools used were mean, pearson r and path analysis. The result showed that the level of ethical climate was very high, team member effectiveness was very high and organizational efficacy was very high among police officers. Further, it was revealed that there is significance of the relationship of ethical climate on organizational efficacy; organizational efficacy on team member effectiveness; and ethical climate on team member effectiveness. Furthermore, organizational efficacy has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers.

Keywords:- education, ethical climate, team member effectiveness, organizational efficiency, mediation, path analysis, Philippines.

I. INTRODUCTION

Police organizations are confronted with various problems in the field especially in terms of team failure. The fall short of the community policemen to work effectively as a team in the organization creates a negative impact to their overall organizational effectiveness in general. In fact, most police departments encountered conflicts and rivalry among team members of the police team due to personality problems and disagreement with their plans and ideas on how to solve and eliminate crimes. Further, most studies had revealed that ineffective team work performance of police officers would have negative impacts on the organization and their reliability concerning the challenges associated with safely maintaining life and property from the citizens' viewpoint. Inevitably, such

a poor situation would result in national decline especially in keeping peace and law enforcement. Further, ineffective team work performance by police officials could negatively influence people's confidence in being safe and secure in the city or locality, and foreign business and investors' confidence in business entities could suffer, which would degrade the country's economic system and inevitably lead to social problems (Chokprachakchat 2011, para. 1-3; Tengpongsthorn 2017, pp. 39-44).

In conjunction, teamwork, especially among law enforcement officers, is a crucial aspect of the job. However, the effectiveness of teams is largely dependent on leadership's commitment to teamwork and the willingness of individuals to be strong team members. Police leaders need to be aware of the distinct dysfunctions that could threaten effective teamwork within agencies. A police force is tasked with the responsibility of protecting the citizens within its jurisdiction and enforcing laws that relate to public safety, thus rely on teamwork among members and between different departments to serve effectively. Specifically, police organizations use teamwork in their training programs and emergency response procedures (Beshears 2015, para. 11-13; Hartman 2017, Para. 9-11). Subsequently, team development is essential in bringing the team's full potential (Tuckman 2021, para. 1).

Moreover, researches revealed the link between and among ethical climate, organizational efficacy and team member effectiveness. In other organizations, it was found out that ethical climate appears to be associated with effective team performance. Additionally, employees who work in ethical environment will be more effective with their job and more loyal than employees who work in an unethical environment. Team interest and performance were perceived higher in an organization where there is high ethical climate (Stanislaus 2017, p. 1). On the other hand, organizational efficacy also influences performance of team. For instance, researches revealed that there is positive relationship between collective organizational efficacy and engagement of people within a group in an organization working collectively as team. In addition, it was shown how employees' organizational efficacy perceptions affect work outcomes and predict their job performance and helping behavior in a team.

It was highlighted how organizational efficacy improve outcomes of team members (Du, Shin & Choi 2014, p. 65; Kravchenko & Zappala 2017, pp. 368-369).

Furthermore, the researcher has not come across of a study that dealt on the mediating influence of organizational efficacy on the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers. It was in this context that the researcher is interested to determine whether the organizational efficacy has a mediating influence on the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers in Davao City as this can raise concern to the intended beneficiaries of this study and possibly develop action plans to improve organizational efficacy, ethical climate and team member effectiveness of the Philippine National Police, thus, the need to conduct this study.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The quantitative, non-experimental design of research using correlational technique was used in this study. Correlational technique is a non-experimental design, where researcher examines the relationship between two or more variables in a natural setting without manipulation or control. In correlational studies, the researchers examine the strength of associations between variables by looking how change in one variable was correlated with change in the other variable (Bhandari 2021, para. 1).

Moreover, a mediation model was used in this study. Mediation model is one that seeks to identify and explicate the mechanism or process that underlies an observed relationship between an independent variable (ethical climate) and a dependent variable (team member effectiveness) via the inclusion of a third explanatory variable, known as a mediator variable (organizational efficacy). Rather than hypothesizing a direct causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable, a mediational model hypothesizes that the independent variable influences the mediator variable, which in turn influences the dependent variable. Thus, the mediator variable serves to clarify the nature of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables. In other words, mediating relationships occur when a third variable plays an important role in governing the relationship between the other two variables (Fairchild & MacKinnon 2009, para. 3).

The study was conducted among selected police stations in Davao City. Shown in Figure 2 is the map of the Philippines highlighting the location of the city of Davao City. Davao City is a highly urbanized city in the island of Mindanao. The city has a total land area of 2,443.61 km² (943.48 sq mi), and has a population of 1,632,991 based on the 2015 census, making it the largest city in the Philippines in terms of land area. The city is also the third-most-populous city in the Philippines. Further, Davao City is located in the southeastern part of Mindanao, lying in the grid squares of 6 58' to 7 34' N latitude, and 125 14' to 125 40' E longitude. It is bounded on the north by Davao Province; on the east partly by Davao Province and Davao Gulf; on the south by Davao del Sur; and on the west

by North Cotabato. Davao City Proper is approximately 946 aerial kilometers or 588 statute miles, southeast of Manila. Because of its strategic location, Davao City was developed as a regional trade center from Southern Mindanao; international trade.

The researcher opted to choose the selected police stations in Davao city since currently he is the Chief of Police of one of the Districts in the city. As a police official, it was easy for him to connect and ask permission to the concerned heads of each station. Furthermore, assessing the ethical climate, organizational efficacy and team member effectiveness among police officers is deemed necessary and significant among police stations in the city as they cover a wide scope of law enforcement responsibility especially in terms of employee management and community relations. Based on experience, he observed that the team member effectiveness among police officers quite depreciated that led to the unpleasant image of PNP due to the unharmonized courses of action towards a certain issue or conflict.

The respondents of the study were the 367 out 2218 police non-commissioned officers among police stations in Davao City. From the total population, the sample size was enough for the study with 95% level of confidence and 5% margin of error (Raosoft, 2010 as cited in Memon et al., 2020, p. v). To determine the research respondents, stratified random sampling was used. Stratified random sampling is a sampling design used when population is heterogeneous. The elements were formed into sub-groups called "strata" that is commonly based on gender, age, ethnicity, socioeconomic status (Alvi 2016, p. 20). This sampling design was preferred by the researcher because this study aimed to glean information from police officers among police stations in Davao City that have different work experiences and through this, the researcher was able to get a deeper insight since the respondents are the ones who provided the appropriate data for the study.

In the selection of the research respondents, inclusion and exclusion criteria were considered. The respondents were bonafide police officers whose plantilla numbers were in the Philippine National Police. Police officers were willing to submit themselves and were permitted by their station commanders to undergo the survey to be conducted. Those police officers who voluntarily agreed with the informed consent were included in the survey, hence, police officers who clearly confessed their denial were excluded from the study. Also, the approval and recommendation of the station commanders were also considered in the inclusion of respondents. Further, the researcher considered the police officers personally decided to withdraw or back out during the actual administration of the survey questionnaires despite station commander's prior approval.

The questionnaire for ethical climate was adapted from Ergun, Yaldiran and Yener (2012, pp. 724-733) which was modified to fit in to the study and subjected to the validation of the experts. The ethical climate questionnaire has the following indicators: social responsibility, rules and professional codes, and personal morality and interest.

In evaluating the ethical climate, the five orderable gradations with their respective range of means and descriptions were used as follows:

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the items related to ethical climate are always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the items related to ethical climate are often evident.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the items related to ethical climate are sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	This means that the items related to ethical climate are seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the items related to ethical climate are never evident.

Further, the questionnaire for team member effectiveness was adapted from Ohland et al. (2012, pp. 609-630). It was modified to fit in to the study and subjected to the validation of the experts. The questionnaire for the team member effectiveness has the following indicators: contributing to the team's work, interacting with teammates, keeping the team on track, expecting quality, and having relevant knowledge, skills and abilities.

In evaluating the team member effectiveness of police officers, the following range of means with its descriptions were used.

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the items related to team member effectiveness of police officers are always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the items related to team member effectiveness of police officers are often evident
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the items related to team member effectiveness of police officers are sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	This means that the items related to team member effectiveness of police officers are seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the items related to team member effectiveness of police officers are never evident.

Moreover, the questionnaire for organizational efficacy was adapted from McDowell (2013, pp. 1-19). It was modified to fit in to the study and subjected to the validation of the experts. In evaluating organizational efficacy, the following range of means with its descriptions were used.

Rating Scale	Descriptive Rating	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Very High	This means that the items related to organizational efficacy are always evident.
3.40 - 4.19	High	This means that the items related to organizational efficacy are often evident.
2.30 – 3.39	Moderate	This means that the items related to organizational efficacy are sometimes evident.
1.80 – 2.29	Low	This means that the items related to organizational efficacy are seldom evident.
1.00 – 1.79	Very Low	This means that the items related to organizational efficacy are never evident

The first draft of the research instrument was submitted to the research adviser for comments, suggestions and recommendations to improve its presentation with the corrections to be included and integrated. The final copies were submitted to panel of experts for refinement. The final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments and suggestions given by the expert validators before the gathering of data. The consolidated results from the experts obtained an average weighted mean of 4.42 which has a verbal description of Very Good.

Further, before the administration of the research instrument, a pilot testing was done to selected police officers who were not the respondents of the study. The survey questionnaire for the pilot test was subjected to the reliability testing to establish using Internal Consistency Method. This was the most appropriate method to use since the test contains

dichotomously scored items which the examinee either passes or fails in an item. For the independent variable, ethical climate, it gained a Cronbach Alpha of 0.814 with mean inter-item correlation of 0.540 which means good internal consistency. For the dependent variable, team member effectiveness, it gained a Cronbach Alpha of 0.903 with mean inter-item correlation of 0.627 which means excellent internal consistency. While the mediating variable, organizational efficacy, garnered a Cronbach Alpha of 0.845 with mean inter-item correlation of 0.717 which means good internal consistency.

In the collection of data, the researcher took the following steps since Davao City is under community lockdown due to the surge of COVID-19 within the city and that all government offices are advised to observe social distancing and paperless transactions. First, a letter was sent to

the City Director, Davao City Police Office – PCOL KIRBY JHON B. KRAFT for the permission to conduct the study. Upon approval, verbal instruction from CITY DIRECTOR to the Station Commanders to accommodate and support the researcher throughout the conduct of the study to the 367 police non-commissioned officers. The researcher personally distributed and administered the research instrument on the ethical climate, team member effectiveness and organizational efficacy to ensure 100 percent retrieval of the questionnaires.

During the online administration of the survey questionnaire, the researcher made sure that the work of the police officers was not interrupted. However, the researcher had experienced unexpected circumstances during the conduct of the study. Some of the respondents did not immediately respond to the online survey. Accordingly, some respondent finds hard time to access to the online survey due to the busy schedule in which respondents are directed to conduct Recorda to all barangay in their AOR. But with the assistance of the station commanders and some of his colleagues, he was able to attain the target number of respondents for the administration of the questionnaire. Furthermore, during the administration of questionnaire, the possible questions and clarifications of the respondents were personally addressed to the researcher via email, text and messenger. After the respondents have completely answered the necessary data needed in the online questionnaire, the researcher retrieved responds via Google Form. Also, a Certificate of Appearance was secured from the Station Commanders concerned to vouch that the researcher honestly collected the data online from the research respondents of the study. After the successful retrieval of the questionnaires, the data were

collated and tabulated. Then, appropriate statistical tools were employed to derive the necessary data for interpretation and further analysis.

III. RESULT

A. Ethical Climate

The first objective of this study was to determine the level of ethical climate in the Philippine National Police organization as perceived by the police officers themselves, which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: social responsibility, rules and professional codes, and personal morality and interest.

Shown in Table 1 are the data on the level of ethical climate among police officers. The level of ethical climate among police officers gets an overall mean of 4.55 or very high, with a standard deviation of 0.42. This means that the ethical climate among police officers is always evident.

Data reveals that the domain of ethical climate among police officers that yielded the highest mean score, as shown in Table 1, is personal morality and interest, with a mean rating of 4.70 or very high and a standard deviation of 0.40, which means it is always evident. Further, social responsibility is the second-highest indicator, with a mean score of 4.61 or very high, and a standard deviation of 0.47, which is always evident. Rules and professional codes follow this, as the least indicator, albeit still very high, which gained the mean score of 4.33 with standard deviations of 0.57, which can be described as always evident.

Table 1:- Level of Ethical Climate among Police Officers in Davao City

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Social responsibility	0.47	4.61	very high
Rules and professional codes	0.57	4.33	very high
Personal morality and interest	0.40	4.70	very high
Overall	0.42	4.55	very high

B. Team Member Effectiveness

The second objective was to determine the level of team member effectiveness among police officers, which was measured through a survey questionnaire with the following indicators: contributing to the team's work, interacting with teammates, keeping the team on track, expecting quality, and having relevant knowledge, skills and abilities.

Shown in Table 2 are the data on the level of team member effectiveness among police officers. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.72 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.38, and this indicates that the team member effectiveness of police officers is always evident.

Data reveals that the domain of team member effectiveness among police officers that yielded the highest

mean score, as shown in Table 2, contributes to the team's work with a mean rating of 4.75 or very high and a standard deviation of 0.39, which means it is always evident. Moreover, interacting with teammates is the second-highest indicator, with a mean score of 4.74 or very high and a standard deviation of 0.40, which is always evident. Keeping the team on track ranked third with a mean score of 4.73 or very high and a standard deviation of 0.41, which means it is always evident. Likewise, expecting quality was the fourth-highest indicator with the mean scores of 4.71 or very high and a standard deviation of 0.44, which means it is always evident. This is followed by having relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities as the least indicator, albeit still very high, which gained a mean score of 4.66 with standard deviations of 0.46, which can be described as always evident.

Table 2:- Level of Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers in Davao City

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Contributing to the team’s work	0.39	4.75	very high
Interacting with teammates	0.40	4.74	very high
Keeping the team on track	0.41	4.73	very high
Expecting quality	0.44	4.72	very high
Having relevant knowledge, skills and abilities	0.46	4.66	very high
Overall	0.38	4.72	very high

C. Organizational Efficacy

The third objective was to determine the level of organizational efficacy among police officers in Davao City. Shown in Table 3 are the data on the level of organizational efficacy among police officers measured using a 9-item survey

questionnaire. Computations yielded a grand mean of 4.73 or very high with a standard deviation of 0.41, indicating that the organizational efficacy among police officers is always evident.

Table 3:- Level of Organizational Efficacy among Police Officers

	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Organizational Efficacy	0.41	4.73	very high

D. Significance of the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers

One important purpose of this study was to determine whether or not the ethical climate has a significant relationship with the team member effectiveness among police officers in Davao City. The results of the computations are shown in Table 4. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of ethical climate and the level of team member effectiveness among police officers is 0.706 with $p < 0.01$, which means that ethical climate is significantly associated with the team member effectiveness of police officers. Hence, the null hypothesis 1 (HO1) that there is no

significant relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers is rejected.

Further, when the domains of ethical climate such as the social responsibility, rules and professional codes, and personal morality and interest were correlated to the team member effectiveness of police officers, the results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.652, 0.541, and 0.694, with the p-values of less than 0.01, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the overall team member effectiveness among police officers.

Table 4:- Significance of the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers in Davao City

Ethical Climate	Team Member Effectiveness					
	CTW	IWT	KTT	EQ	HRKSA	Overall
Social Responsibility	.585** (.000)	.630** (.000)	.601** (.000)	.575** (.000)	.579** (.000)	.652** (.000)
Rules and Professional Codes	.435** (.000)	.493** (.000)	.499** (.000)	.494** (.000)	.534** (.000)	.541** (.000)
Personal Morality and Interest	.673** (.000)	.683** (.000)	.627** (.000)	.589** (.000)	.605** (.000)	.694** (.000)
Overall	.627** (.000)	.674** (.000)	.547** (.000)	.623** (.000)	.646** (.000)	.706** (.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

E. Significance of the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Organizational Efficacy among Police Officers

Another purpose of this study was to determine whether or not ethical climate has a significant relationship with the organizational efficacy of police officers. The results of the computations are shown in Table 5. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of ethical climate and the level of organizational efficacy of police officers is 0.665 with $p < 0.01$, which means that the ethical climate is significantly associated with the organizational efficacy of police officers. Hence, the null hypothesis 1 (HO1) that there is no significant relationship

between the ethical climate and organizational efficacy among police officers is rejected.

Likewise, when the domains of ethical climate such as the social responsibility, rules and professional codes, and personal morality and interest were correlated to the organizational efficacy of police officers, the results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.611, 0.501, and 0.677, with the p-values of less than 0.01, respectively, which can be all interpreted as significant. These factors are significantly related to the overall organizational efficacy among police officers.

Table 5:- Significance of the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Organizational Efficacy among Police Officers in Davao City

Ethical Climate	Organizational Efficacy
Social Responsibility	.611** (.000)
Rules and Professional Codes	.501** (.000)
Personal Morality and Interest	.677** (.000)
Overall	.665** (.000)

F. Significance of the Relationship between the Organizational Efficacy and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers

This present study also aimed to determine whether or not organizational efficacy has a significant relationship with the team member effectiveness of police officers. The results of the computations are shown in Table 6. As shown in the table, the overall r-value on the correlation between the level of organizational efficacy and the level team member effectiveness is 0.815 with $p < 0.01$, which means that the organizational efficacy is significantly associated with the team member effectiveness of police officers. Hence, the null hypothesis 1 (HO1) that there is no significant relationship

between the organizational efficacy and team member effectiveness among police officers is rejected.

In addition, when organizational efficacy is correlated with the domains of team member effectiveness, such as the contributing to the team’s work, interacting with teammates, keeping the team on track, expecting quality, and having relevant knowledge, skills and abilities, results of the computation yielded the r-values of 0.739, 0.751, 0.743, 0.713, 0.776, and 0.815, respectively, with p-values of less than 0.01, which can be all interpreted as significant. Hence, these factors are significantly related to the overall organizational efficacy of police officers.

Table 6:- Significance of the Relationship between the Organizational Efficacy and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers in Davao City

	Team Member Effectiveness					
	CTW	TWT	KTT	EQ	HRKSA	Overall
Organizational Efficacy	.739** (.000)	.751** (.000)	.743** (.000)	.713** (.000)	.776* (.000)	.815** (.000)

G. Significance of the Mediation of Organizational Efficacy on the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers

By using Path Analysis, the result revealed that paths EC (X) to OE (M); EC (X) to TME (Y); and OE (M) to TME (Y) are significant; this results to a partial mediation computation; thus, OE partially mediates the relationship between EC and TME. Furthermore, the result of the mediation computation shown in Figure 3 the indirect paths revealed that for every

unit increase in Ethical Climate, there is a corresponding 0.67 unit increase in the Organizational Efficacy of police officers. At the same time, for every unit increase in Organizational Efficacy, there is a corresponding 0.62 unit increase in the Team Member Effectiveness of police officers. Also, the direct path revealed that for every unit increase in Ethical Climate, there is a corresponding 0.29 unit increase in the Team Member Effectiveness of police officers. This indicates that Organizational Efficacy is only one of the reasons how

Ethical Climate can influence the Team Member Effectiveness of police officers. Since it is only partial mediation, it could not be claimed that Organizational Efficacy is the very reason how Ethical Climate can influence Team Member Effectiveness of police officers.

This further implies that, with partial mediation, Ethical Climate has both direct and indirect effects on the Team Member Effectiveness of police officers. The direct effect is not mediated, whereas the indirect effect is transmitted

through EC-OE-TME. This further implies that the team member effectiveness of police officers can be heightened by ethical climate and can be augmented by passing through an improved organizational efficacy. Consequently, organizational efficacy mediates the ethical climate of the police organization for better team member effectiveness of police officers. These findings suggest the rejection of the null hypothesis 2 (HO2) that there is no significant mediation of organizational efficacy on the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers.

Table 7:- Significance of the Relationship between the Organizational Efficacy and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers in Davao City

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
OE	<---	EC	.654	.038	17.064	***	par 2
TME	<---	EC	.268	.034	7.844	***	par 1
TME	<---	OE	.573	.035	16.452	***	par 3

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Level of Ethical Climate among Police Officers

The very high level of ethical climate among police officers is due to the very high rating given by the respondents on the indicators of social responsibility, rules and professional codes, and personal morality and interest. Among these three domains, personal morality and interest was the highest, followed by social responsibility, and rules and professional codes. It implies that the police officers have a very high level of personal morality and interest. This means that they display moral principles and show great interest in the welfare of others in the police organization. This is in conjunction with the ideas of Ergun, Yaldiran and Yener (2012, pp. 724-733) which revealed that people in the organization with high personal morality and interest protect their interests above other considerations. Also, they decide what is right and wrong inside the organization.

Further, data implies that police officers show very high social responsibility, specifically in looking for solutions to existing problems within the community. Police officers consider the effects of every decision the police organization has on the community's constituents. At the same time, they ensure that all police officers' welfare in the organization is not compromised when making decisions. This expands the idea of some authors (Palmer 2015, pp. 119-132; Wicks 2017, para. 1-2), which stated that an organization with a high sense of social responsibility incorporates measures meant to protect and improve the welfare of society as a whole. With this idea, police officers display the obligation to act for the benefit of the community at large.

Moreover, the results indicate those police officers have very high adherence to rules and professional codes. They strictly follow legal and professional standards. Police officers stick by the police organizational regulations and procedures. They do this efficiently because they believe doing this is always right. This substantiates the ideas of several researchers (Martin & Cullen 2016, pp. 175-194; Venezia et al. 2010, pp. 77-85), which expressed that people of the organization must

recognize the rules ethical climate. Making decisions should be based on the organization's general regulations and codes of conduct. Hence, every organization's decision is driven by established rules and standards. Similarly, some authors (Hort , Manning & Shacklock 2011, pp. 51-65; Lombardo 2015, para. 2) mentioned that a high level of rules and professional codes means that people obey the organization's established procedures, practices, and policies.

B. Level of Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers

The very high level of team member effectiveness is due to the very high rating given by the respondents on the indicators contributing to the team's work; interacting with teammates; keeping the team on track; expecting quality, and having relevant knowledge, skills and abilities. Among the five domains, contributing to the team's work was the highest indicator, followed by interacting with teammates, keeping the team on track, expecting quality, and having relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities. The very high level of police officers' ability to contribute to the team's work implies that police officers display a fair share and timely and helpful attitudes at work. They attend meeting prepared. These police officers fulfill responsibilities and accurately complete work in the team, especially when facing difficult situations. This is in line with the study of various authors (Bondigas 2019, para. 1; Eikenberry 2016, para. 15; Ohland et al. 2012, pp. 609-630), which avowed that in an organizational team, it is essential to include all team members in the planning process to make sure that everyone embraces the shared responsibility at work. The team's success depends on the active and timely involvement of the members in helping other members develop and achieve goals and work processes. Also, the members' ability to share and contribute ideas will help the team to be successful in realizing organizational goals. Relative to this, Emberlin (2018, para. 1-16) stipulated that when police officers as team members are invested in their roles and contributions, they have the highest probability of a successful team outcome.

In parallel, the very high level of the ability of police officers to interact with teammates implies that police officers communicate effectively with their teams. They listen to other co-police officers to solicit ideas from them and exchange information promptly. Also, everyone in their team accepts feedback and uses it to improve the overall police performance. This is in connection with some researchers' ideas (Leonard 2018, para. 10; Ohland et al. 2012, pp. 609-630), which explain it is important for people inside the team to have facilitated effective communication in the team. They should have heard what teammates had to say about issues that affected the team. Thus, everyone considers team input on essential matters before going ahead. In addition, positive interactions among team members increase good feelings, boost morale and improve work satisfaction. Similarly, Esan (2017, pp. 39-43) said those police officers are expected to be effective communicators in law enforcement. In policing, having effective communication and interaction at work resulted in increased trust from members of the public, increased officer safety, efficiency in resolving calls for service, and positive relationships being built within the community they serve.

In addition, the very high level of the ability of the police officers to keep the team on track indicates that each police officer stays aware of the team's progress by assessing external factors that have influenced their performance. Also, police officers provide constructive feedback and help each plan and organize their work. This is to make sure that everyone understands essential information and stays motivated to their work best. This is an addition to the contention of some authors (Ohland et al., 2012), who pointed out that to keep the team on track, all members should help set clear goals and be excited about the team's mission. This evident through their ability to plan, organize and involve team members. Further, in the study of Dong et al. (2019, pp. 3-9), in the police organization, police officers should consider the importance of having the ability to influence others who work to achieve goals and objectives. In their work, planning, organizing, and monitoring are vital functions.

Moreover, the very high level of expected quality as an indicator of team member effectiveness of police officers implies that in their team, everyone is expected to produce high-quality work or high standards in performing their tasks as police officers. This corroborates previous researchers (Ohland et al., 2012), which emphasized that people working in a team must collaboratively adopt a quality mindset of producing high-quality services. Each team member should feel responsible for the outcome of anything connected with the service. Hence, quality will be attained through teamwork. In the same vein. In their study, Alpert, Flynn and Piquero (2001, p. 91) revealed that police officers must ensure quality police performance at work. This quality is conformance to customer needs, a fundamental component of community policing wherein the customer or consumer is the community. The quality performance or productivity also means the ability to accomplish their mission and consequently collaboratively positively affect the quality of life in the communities they serve and how they solve problems.

Lastly, data showed a very high level of having relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities in the team. This means those police officers have the skills and expertise at work. They can clearly define how they can perform their other team members' jobs in their organization. This relates to Hanaysha's (2016, pp. 303-304) idea, which emphasized the importance of team knowledge, skills, and abilities. Employees whose teams had been together longer and those in large organizations were more likely to report strong team skills. Teams with team skills reported higher conflict resolution, goal setting, and planning skills. Further, the study by Oliva and Compton (2010, para. 3) mentioned their research on the importance of knowledge, skills, abilities, and other officer characteristics to effective community-oriented policing. In the police organization, an emphasis must also be placed on developing and implementing police recruit training and continuing education curriculums that are cognitive and include problem-solving, decision-making, and interpersonal exercises.

C. Level of Organizational Efficacy among Police Officers

Show very high social responsibility, specifically in looking for solutions to existing problems within the community. Police officers consider the effects The very high level of organizational efficacy among police officers is due to the very high rating given by the respondents on the different aspects of organizational efficacy. Data implies that police officers can perform their duties well as expected by constituents in the community. They showcase excellent job skills and consequently affect good for the people in the society. Police officers' good performance is evident in their outcomes, especially in solving crimes and other community-related issues. This substantiates the findings of various authors (Capone & Petrillo 2015, para. 1; Petitta & Borgogni 2011, para. 1), which stated that organizational efficacy has positive influences on different aspects of organization life, among them performance. Love et al. (2021, pp. 1331-1345) emphasized the critical role of self-efficacy in how police officers behave and interact with others in their professional responsibilities.

Also, Yesberg and Bradford (2021, pp. 417-430) said that the collective efficacy of police officers has essential benefits for crime prevention. Likewise, Rodrigues (2010, pp. 28-38) presented aspects of perceived police efficacy. This includes a sense of community, which is related to individual belonging and attachment to the community and trust and influence among the community residents. Also, police efficacy refers to the ability to meet the shared expectations of the community for the social control of public spaces.

D. Significance of the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers

Data revealed that ethical climate is significantly associated with the team member effectiveness of police officers. The domains of ethical climate such as social responsibility, rules and professional codes, and personal morality and interest were correlated to the team member effectiveness of police officers. This further implies that police teams attain productivity if there is an increased work ethical climate. This supports the contention of previous studies

(Stanislaus 2017, p. 1), which exposed that ethical climate appears to be associated with effective team performance. Additionally, employees who work in an ethical environment will be more effective with their job and more loyal than employees who work in an unethical environment. Team interest and performance were perceived to be higher in an organization with a high ethical climate.

In conjunction, this study is aligned with the statement of Nystrom, Ramamurthy, and Wilson (2022, para. 1), which stated that work climate plays a crucial role in a team. Specifically, Acikgoza and Gonsel (2011, p. 921), explained that a work climate having vision and management support has direct and positive influences on team effectiveness. In addition, Ergun, Yaldiran and Yener (2012, pp. 724-733) stipulated that in an organization where people work as a team, each work engagement is positively and significantly related to ethical climate. In particular, the social responsibility climate has a more significant effect on teamwork engagement.

E. Significance of the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Organizational Efficacy among Police Officers

Data revealed that ethical climate is significantly associated with the organizational efficacy of police officers. The domains of ethical climate such as social responsibility, rules and professional codes, and personal morality and interest were correlated to the organizational efficacy of police officers as leaders in the community. This implies that the ethical climate in the police organization contributes to the overall police organizational efficacy at work. This aligns with several authors (Tahir 2020, para. 14-15) who state that a positive work climate also leads to higher leader efficacy. Hence, work climate can be linked to an employee and organizational outcomes, making it a vital construct and tool for leaders. Similarly, this expands the study's findings by Hort, Manning and Shacklock (2011, pp. 51-65), which avowed that different types of ethical climates in organizations would affect both self-efficacy and their capacity to deliver ethical outcomes.

F. Significance of the Relationship between the Organizational Efficacy and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers

Data revealed that organizational efficacy is significantly associated with the team member effectiveness of police officers. Organizational efficacy is correlated with the domains of team member effectiveness, such as contributing to the team's work, interacting with teammates, keeping the team on track, expecting quality, and having relevant knowledge, skills and abilities. Hence, police officers' teamwork success is achieved if everyone in the policing organization develops higher organizational efficacy at work. This result of the study affirmed the ideas of several authors (Du, Shin & Choi 2014, p. 65; Kravchenko & Zappala 2017, pp. 368-369), which pointed out that organizational efficacy also influences the performance of the team. These studies revealed a positive relationship between collective organizational efficacy and engagement of people within a group in an organization working collectively as a team. In

addition, it was shown how employees' organizational efficacy perceptions affect work outcomes and predict their job performance and helping behavior in a team. Hence, organizational efficacy improves the outcomes of team members.

G. Significance of the Mediation of Organizational Efficacy on the Relationship between the Ethical Climate and Team Member Effectiveness among Police Officers

The path analysis revealed that organizational efficacy partially mediates the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers. This indicates that organizational efficacy is only one of the reasons how ethical climate can influence the team member effectiveness of police officers. It implies that the team member effectiveness of police officers can be heightened by ethical climate and can be augmented by passing through an improved organizational efficacy. Hence, organizational efficacy mediates the ethical climate of the police organization for better team member effectiveness of police officers. This strengthens the previous propositions (Stanislaus 2017, p. 1), which exposed that team performance was perceived as higher in an organization with a high ethical climate. At the same time, Hort, Manning & Shacklock (2011, pp. 51-65), emphasized that different ethical climates in organizations will affect workers' self-efficacy. When this self-efficacy is increased, other authors (Du, Shin & Choi 2014, p. 65; Kravchenko & Zappala 2017, pp. 368-369) avowed that it also influences team performance in general.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Organizational efficacy has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers. It can be explained that organizational efficacy is only one of the reasons how ethical climate can influence the team member effectiveness of police officers since organizational efficacy partially mediates the ethical climate of the police organization for better team member effectiveness of police officers. Also, this study confirmed the propositions of previous researchers, which stated the significant link between and among organizational efficacy, ethical climate, and team member effectiveness. This supports the contention of Stanislaus (2017, p. 1), which exposed that ethical climate appears to be associated with effective team performance. Similarly, Acikgoza and Gonsel (2011, p. 921), pointed out how work climate directly and positively influences team effectiveness in which people work as a team having work engagement. Further, the results align with the proposition of Hort, Manning & Shacklock (2011, pp. 51-65), which stated that the ethical climate in organizations would affect the self-efficacy of workers.

The study revealed the domains of ethical climate among police officers; the rules and professional codes got the lowest mean; thus, the researcher recommends that the Philippine National Police administrators conduct related retooling activities which aim to re-orient the police officers of the organizational, legal and professional standards. Every chief of police in various local government units may organize in-service seminars and organizational system practices to ensure

that all police officers under the unit maintain familiarity and obey police organizational rules and procedures.

Moreover, in terms of team member effectiveness, a result showed that police officers got the lowest mean score in having relevant knowledge, skills, and abilities. The researcher highly recommends that the PNP administrators strengthen training development programs for police officers. Training development activities may focus on retooling police officers on their ability to deter crimes and assuring the community through high-visibility policing. Also, training includes knowledge on patrolling assigned areas and monitoring activities to protect people and property. Further, they may be trained to improve their skills in investigating crimes and even with community relations.

Additionally, results showed a very high level of organizational efficacy of police officers; hence, it is relevant and timely for police officers to personally find ways to maintain their efficacy in producing outcomes in solving crimes and other community-related issues. By continually engaging themselves in the community, they may be able to augment the sense of community as one aspect of organizational efficacy. Further, community engagement of police officers will help them improve their ability to meet the shared expectations of the community for the social control of public spaces.

In addition, results of the study showed that organizational efficacy partially mediates the relationship between the ethical climate and team member effectiveness among police officers; hence, it is recommended for the police organizations to augment police officers' organizational efficacy and ethical climate in terms of social responsibility, rules, and professional codes, and personal morality and interest since these are contributing factors of team member effectiveness among police officers. Developing both organizational efficacy and ethical climate can be done by implementing quality assurance systems and practices explicitly focusing on establishing organizational strategic plans and indicators of police performance, especially in teamwork. Likewise, future researchers may conduct a similar study to validate further and extend the present research work results. Additionally, mixed-method research may be undertaken to expand the study's results, providing specific explanations to the significant findings of the quantitative approach.

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